

A Note on the Complexity of the Magnetic Properties of Elements in the Colloidal State.

By S. S. BHATNAGAR.

The magnetic properties of elements, in the colloidal state, have been investigated in only a few cases. Honda (*Ann. Physik*, 1910, *iv*, 32, 1027) and Owen (*ibid.*, 1912, *iv*, 37, 657), were the first to investigate colloidal bismuth and show that it is about one third as diamagnetic as the metal crystals. Results in the same direction have recently been obtained by Vaidyanathan (*Nature*, 1930, 125, 672 and *Indian J. Phys.*, 1930, 3, 559) in the case of graphite, bismuth and antimony. The influence of crystalline structure on the magnetic properties of elements is well known from the work of Faraday and Tyndall, but generally the effects are of a much smaller order of magnitude than those obtained in the case of the above-named elements. It, therefore, appeared desirable to exclude the following possibilities before accepting the proffered explanation of this effect.—(1) The adsorption of gases from the atmosphere. (2) The formation of the oxide on the surface when the substance is powdered to colloidal dimensions. Powdered bismuth, as well as colloidal bismuth, prepared by Bredig's method, were therefore tested for the presence of the oxide by Muir's test (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, 31, 658) and found to contain quite appreciable amounts of it. The melting points of the powder and colloidal bismuth were also found to be different from that of the metal.

It now remained to examine whether the oxides of bismuth were sufficiently paramagnetic or much less diamagnetic than the metal itself, to account for a part of the observed changes in diamagnetism. BiO was therefore prepared by Mr. Mulkh Raj according to Schneider's method (*Ann. Phys. Chem.*, 1853, 88, 45). This substance is extremely unstable excepting when in solution with the metal, as is the case with many other suboxides. The susceptibility of this very wet powder was determined by Mr. R. N. Mathur, M.Sc. by the Interference Balance (*Phil. Mag.*, 1929, *vii*, 8, 1041). It was found to be very feebly diamagnetic, and if the susceptibility of water present be

accounted for, it might leave the black residue slightly paramagnetic. That BiO should be paramagnetic is also clear from the fact that it is a compound with an odd molecular number. Besides Williams (*Physical Rev.*, 1926, ii, 28, 167) has shown that BiO₂ is definitely paramagnetic and the presence of this material has not been excluded in previous investigations on colloidal bismuth.

In order to show further that the tarnishing of the surface is of enough consequence, a piece of the metal was dipped in dilute nitric acid, so that a black tarnish was formed on its surface. This piece was then washed with water to remove any soluble nitrates, etc. and the specific susceptibility of the tarnished metal was found to be much less than that of the pure metal.

It is, therefore, necessary to be cautious in advancing views regarding anomalous diamagnetism of substances on powdering or colloidalisation. From the study of steel, it is abundantly clear that small amounts of chemical substances, which form solid solution with iron, play an important part in the magnetic properties of steel and hence the laws that govern the change of magnetic properties in solid solutions should be discovered before any definite conclusions could be arrived at. From our experiments, it is clear that at least a good part of the effect in bismuth is due to the formation of the black oxide.

The investigation of copper and other elements of its family is also very important in this connection. Unlike bismuth and antimony, their susceptibilities increase on melting. Moreover, while the atoms of Cu, Ag and Au are paramagnetic according to the experiments of Stern and Gerlach, the metal crystals are diamagnetic. In such cases diamagnetism should, therefore, increase if powdering alone is of any consequence.

Experiments on the thermal, chemical and colloidal changes of diamagnetism of the above elements are in progress and the results will shortly be communicated for publication. We are also investigating as to how the susceptibility of a diamagnetic or a paramagnetic substance varies when it is coated all over the surface with a paramagnetic or a diamagnetic material respectively.